

and spectrophotometric results indicate the formation of intermediate complex between Cr^{VI} and hydroxy acid.

It may be also mentioned here that unlike glycollic acid, C—H bond on the carbon atom is absent in salicylic and phenylsalicylate which form complexes with divalent and trivalent transition metal ions. The reaction may be explain on the basis of the formation of free radicals, e.g. RR'C(OH), which reacts with Cr^{VI} to form stable products ketone and Cr^{VI}, may be considered as

The formation of free radicals, however, could not be detected, since all the experiments are performed in the presence of air. The presence of intermediate valence states of chromium has been indicated by the decrease in the reaction rate in the presence of manganese(II). The appreciable increase in the reaction rate on adding bidentate ligands (Table 4) has been explained due to a two electron transfer reaction which have been observed by us.

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS OF OXIDATION OF HYDROXY ACIDS BY Cr^{VI}

Acid	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ k cal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ e. u.	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ at 303 K k cal
Salicylic acid	18.5 ± 1.8	13.6 ± 4.6	22.6 ± 2.4
Phenylsalicylate	17.8 ± 2.0	13.12 ± 2.5	21.7 ± 1.5
Gallic acid	15.6 ± 1.3	32.2 ± 2.8	25.27 ± 1.2
Tartaric acid	22.2 ± 2.2	4.03 ± 3.2	23.43 ± 0.8

TABLE 3—INFLUENCE OF Mn^{II} ION ON REACTION

[Mn ²⁺]	k × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	
	(a)	(b)
2.0	1.33 ± 0.92	4.57 ± 0.38
3.0	1.7 ± 0.90	4.24 ± 0.30
(a) [Tartaric acid] = 3.9 × 10 ⁻² M, [Cr ^{VI}] = 2.49 × 10 ⁻³ M, [H ⁺] = 1.39 M.		
(b) [Gallic acid] = 2.0 × 10 ⁻² M, [Cr ^{VI}] = 2.49 × 10 ⁻³ M, [H ⁺] = 1.27 M.		

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF SOME BIDENTATE LIGANDS ON REACTION RATE

2,2'-dipyridyl	k × 10 ⁴ sec ⁻¹	
	(a)	(b)
1.0	5.07 ± 0.45	5.94 ± 0.42
2.0	5.41 ± 0.40	6.87 ± 0.54
(a) [Tartaric acid] = 1.5 × 10 ⁻² M, [Cr ^{VI}] = 2.49 × 10 ⁻³ M, [H ⁺] = 2.54 M.		
(b) [Gallic acid] = 1.5 × 10 ⁻² M, [Cr ^{VI}] = 2.49 × 10 ⁻³ M, [H ⁺] = 1.27 M.		

The course of reduction has been represented as Cr^{VI} → Cr^{IV} → Cr^{II}.

Moreover, it has been observed that some hydroxy acids react with the ions of transition metals to give stable 1 : 2 coordination compounds in solution. Consequently, the formation of 1 : 2 intermediate compound seems unlikely in the present study. The first order rate constants in the presence of Mn^{II} ion were found to be 1.3 × 10⁴, 1.7 × 10⁴ for tartaric acid and 4.57 × 10⁴, 4.24 × 10⁴ for gallic acid. This shows that the rate determining steps is also possibly by a two electron transfer process.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Ionisation Constants of Hydroxytriazenes

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SEVERAL workers¹⁻³ have used spectrophotometric method for the determination of ionisation constants of some hydroxytriazenes. The present communication reports the ionisation constants of seven new hydroxytriazenes derived from 3-hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-phenyltriazene.

Experimental

Hydroxytriazenes were prepared following the method given by Golwalkar⁴ and were identical to the authentic sample. In uv absorption studies, it was observed that in these compounds the absorption maximum appearing around 313 nm shifts to ~350 nm in alkaline medium. This observation was the basis of spectrophotometric method for determining ionisation constants following the reported methods¹⁻³. Absorbance measurements were made at Hitachi Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, using 1.00 cm matched quartz cells and Cambridge pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Procedure: A series of solutions containing different amounts of sodium hydroxide were prepared in volumetric flasks (10 ml) so as to get pH of the final solution between 6.0 and 14.0. Ionic strength was kept at 0.1 using KCl (1.0 M) solution. To this, 1.0 ml freshly prepared ethanolic solution of hydroxytriazene (1.0×10^{-4} M) was added. The solution was diluted to the mark with ethanol and absorbance was measured at 350 nm in each case. From these results, pK values were determined as per the reported methods and are given in Table 1. For comparison sake the reported pK values of parent compounds of different hydroxytriazene series have also been incorporated in the Table.

TABLE 1—pK VALUES OF HYDROXYTRIAZENES

Sl. no.	Hydroxytriazene	pK
1.	3-Hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene*	11.41
2.	3-Hydroxy-3-methyl-1-phenyltriazene**	12.11
3.	3-Hydroxy-3-ethyl-1-phenyltriazene**	12.28
4.	3-Hydroxy-3-n-propyl-1-phenyltriazene**	12.39
5.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-phenyltriazene	10.48
6.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-tolyltriazene	10.59
7.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-chloro-phenyltriazene	10.21
8.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-bromo-phenyltriazene	10.30
9.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-carboxy-phenyltriazene	10.34
10.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-p-methoxy-phenyltriazene	10.50
11.	3-Hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-m-acetyl-phenyltriazene	10.49

* Refs. 1 and 2. ** Ref. 3.

Hydroxytriazenes have been assigned* an intramolecular hydrogen bonded structure and any substituent which has a tendency to weaken the hydrogen bonding will increase its acid character. Thus, the dissociation will depend upon the nature and position of the group present in benzene ring. A perusal of the result given in Table 1 reveals that 3-alkyl substituted hydroxytriazenes have high pK values than the pK value of 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazene. This may be attributed to +I effect of alkyl group which increases in the order methyl < ethyl < propyl. However, pK value of 3-hydroxy-3-isopropyl-1-phenyltriazene is much less. This deviation may be due to steric effect of isopropyl group. The bulky isopropyl group attached

to the 3-nitrogen atom, perhaps, sterically inhibits the formation of intramolecular hydrogen bonded structure, thus reduces its stability and thereby increases the dissociation of proton resulting into lowering in pK value.

The compound 6 has pK value higher than the parent compound 5. This is attributed to +I effect of methyl group at *para* position. The compounds 7 and 8 have pK values lower than the parent compound 5. This is due to -I effect of halogens and it seems that +M effect of halogens is not operative due to strong +M effect of -N=N- group. The decrease in pK values of halogen substituted compounds is as per the decreasing inductive effect of halogens (F > Cl > Br > I). Decrease in pK value of compound 9 may be attributed to -M effect of -COOH group. The pK values of compounds 10 and 11 are comparable to that of the parent compound and as such difficult to explain.

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Effect of Conductance on Mobility of Ions by Paper-electrophoretic Studies

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A large number of separations of inorganic ions by electromigration in paper have been reported¹. But the physical studies on the electromigration of ions in paper were made by only few workers. Effects of valency of ions, pH, temperature, and electroosmotic effect on migrant were studied by various workers²⁻⁷. These studies promoted us to study the effect of conductance on the electrophoretic migration of ion. The present work reports the effect of conductance of migrant and conductance of carrier electrolyte on the electrophoretic migration of cations in the paper. As the mobility of a